

Chemoprofiling of some Himalayan flora : Search for new pharmaceuticals[†]

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Abstract : The Himalayan biodiversity is a great resource for Indian Systems of Medicine. Natural products continue to play an extremely important role but less appreciated aspect is that the plant species not always possess identical chemical constituents even within the same species (having same morphological features). These may possess different chemical metabolites, consequently affecting their medicinal property and their commercial potential. It is, therefore, essential to know the nature of chemical variations within plant species of interest before their use as raw herbal medicines or for production of value added chemicals. This communication presents the potential of Himalayan flora in drug development and reviews the results of chemoprofiling and chemical compositions of some Poaceae, Valerianaceae, Asteraceae, Apiaceae, Lamiaceae, Zingiberaceae and Lauraceae species.

Keywords : Chemoprofiling, natural products, essential oils, Himalayan flora, chemodiversity.

Introduction

Out of more than 2.5 lakh higher plant species spread world over, approximately one-third are medicinally important and the products related to 20,000 plants are marketed as phytochemicals and active chemical ingredients derived from the plants. In the search for new compounds and the identification of compounds for the pharmaceutical industry, natural products continue to play an extremely important role although the advances in drug discovery have been significantly fueled and paralleled by advances in synthetic organic chemistry, structural biology and computational chemistry.

Himalayan floral diversity is bestowed with immense chemical diversity. Because of wide range of structural features, the medicinal plants have served and are still used as a valuable source for the new drug molecules. Consequently, the chemistry of natural products will continue to be the central theme for understanding the chemical processes and for utilizing the new chemical knowledge for sustainable use. Chemodiversity/chemoprofiling studies play key role in solving the problems of bioactivity and commercial utilization of plants materials as drugs, food-

flavour and allied products. These studies may further provide a deeper understanding of the chemistry of life processes and of complex biological and ecological interactions in nature.

Simonsen¹ highlighted the instances of chemical differentiations within some species. Such as, a taxonomist can not differentiate between 'Sofia' and 'Motia' varieties of *Cymbopogon martinii* Staph. grass. But, some differentiation is essential, as the 'Motia' grass yields the well known palmarosa oil while its other form 'Sofia' yields an oil with little or no commercial value. Interestingly, the chemical differentiation of these two materials is simple. The position is similar in many other grasses and other higher plants suggesting the need for differentiation on the chemical basis in addition to morphological species. Although a lot progress has been made since then but chemical basis of classification has not received acceptability to the extent it required.

The bioactivity and commercial utility of a plant is attributed to different classes of secondary metabolites either singly or in combination. Their formation within plants is controlled by various intrinsic and extrinsic factors. Several studies have shown the qualitative and quanti-

[†]In honour of Professor K. C. Joshi on the occasion of his 88th birthday.

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tative changes in these metabolites affecting efficacy of such materials. Besides extrinsic factors like soils, sunlight, moisture etc., genotypic and chemotypic differences are prominent which have similar morphological charac-

ters but chemically distinct with absolutely no visible similarity, thus affecting their usage as material for specific purposes.

At first sight, the chemical differences might be ex-

- 21 a. *cis*-chrysanthenol (R=H)
 21 b. *cis*-chrysanthenyl acetate (R=COCH₃)
 21 c. *cis*-chrysanthenyl isobutyrate (R=COCH(CH₃)₂)
 21 d. *cis*-chrysanthenyl- α -methylbutyrate (R=COCHCH₃CH₂CH₃)
 21 e. *cis*-chrysanthyl angelate (R=C(CH₃)=CHCH₃)(Z)
 21 f. *cis*-chrysanthyl tiglate (R=C(CH₃)=CHCH₃)(E)

- 22 a. *exo*-6-propionyloxy camphor (R=CH₂CH₃)
 22 b. *exo*-6-isobutyryloxy camphor (R=CH(CH₃)₂)
 22 c. *exo*-6-(2-methylbutyryloxy) camphor (R=CHCH₃CH₂(CH₃)₂)
 22 d. *exo*-6-angeloyloxy camphor (R=C(CH₃)=CHCH₃)(Z)
 22 e. *exo*-6-tiglyloxy camphor (R=C(CH₃)=CHCH₃)(E)

pected to be due to soil or climatic conditions but this does not appear to be the case because when grown under similar conditions these retain their chemical identity. This opens up a very difficult chemo-botanical field of research. Whether the chemotaxonomy is made basis or not, chemical study of natural products shall continue its key role in solving the problems of bioactivity and commercial utilization of plants materials as drugs, food-flavours and allied products.

Our investigations on medicinal and aromatic plant species viz. *Cymbopogon*, *Valeriana*, *Nepeta*, *Elsholtzia*, *Hedychium* etc. have revealed existence of chemotypes with wide range of qualitative and quantitative chemical variations. The chemical compositions in some of these are distinct to the extent that the major characteristic bioactive constituents of one chemotype are not noticed in another chemotype within the same species². The environmental, genetic, and physiological factors contribute to the overall phytochemical profile of plants. Chemoprofiling of the plant materials is important for validation and standardization of bioactive chemical markers. Efforts are needed for chemotaxonomic characterization and conservation of genetic and chemical diversity in medicinal and aromatic plants for sustainable utilization of biodiversity. The chemoprofiling and biodiversity researches can contribute for development of new pharmaceuticals, agricultural and industrial products³.

A. Poaceae

Chemical investigations on wild *Cymbopogon* species growing at foot-hills to sub-alpine regions revealed chemotypes within *C. distans* (Steud.) Wats., *C. jwarancusa* (Jones.) schult., *C. martinii* (Roxb.) Wats. and *C. stracheyi* (Hook. f.). *Cymbopogon distans* showed five chemically distinct forms with α -oxobisabolene (**1**) in chemotype-I, neral (**2**), geranial (**3**), geraniol and geranyl acetate in chemotype-II, piperitone (**4**) in chemotype-III, sesquiterpene alcohols viz. 10-epi- γ -eudesmol, eudesmanediol (**5**) in chemotype-IV and *p*-menthenols in chemotype-V as their major compounds⁴⁻⁷. The major compounds of one chemotype were not noticed in other chemotypes at any stage. The essential oil composition of *C. distans* (chemotype-II) is comparable with those of the commercial *Cymbopogon flexuosus* and *C. citratus* with respect to the major aroma chemicals. Our observations

on *C. jwarancusa* differed from the previous reports. Four major components of the oil were identified as (3*R*,4*S*)-(+)-*cis-p*-menth-1-en-3-ol (**6**) and its (3*S*,4*S*)-(–)-*trans* isomer. Other major components were identified as the (1*S*,4*S*)-(–)-*trans-p*-menth-2-en-1-ol and (1*R*,4*S*)-(+)-*cis*-isomers (**7**) along with hinesol (**8**)^{8,9}. Piperitone and car-2-ene are the major constituents of *C. stracheyi*¹⁰. The *cis*- and *trans*-forms of *p*-mentha-2,8-dien-1-ols, *p*-mentha-1(7),8-dien-2-ols, carveols and piperitols in addition to limonene and carvone were also detected in *C. martinii*¹¹. A novel dihemiacetal bismonoterpenoid ‘Cymbodiacetal’ (**9**) was isolated from *C. martinii*¹², formed possibly through unusual head-to-head union of two limonene molecules (methyl substituted ring carbon in limonene and two identical carbon atoms in dihemiacetal possess the same (*R*)-configuration) via *p*-menthadienols, which are the major components of the oil. On comparison of our results with earlier reports on Indian *C. martinii* var. Sofia or Motia, the difference is significant.

B. Valerianaceae

Valeriana wallichii DC., Indian Valerian, has been an ingredient of herbal medicines in Indian systems of medicine and is used as a substitute of European *Valeriana officinalis* and has long been used in Ayurveda and Unani systems of medicine^{13,14}. The crude drugs from roots/rhizomes are used as mild sedatives in pharmaceutical industry. In an effort to determine the chemical diversity within *Valeriana* genera native to Northwestern Himalaya, *V. wallichii*, *V. himalayana* (syn. *V. dioica*), *V. pyrolaefolia* and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* were collected and analysed their terpenoid compositions¹⁵. It was established that *V. wallichii* DC. includes three chemotypes, and *V. hardwickii* var. *arnottiana* was also found to exist as two compositionally distinct chemotypes. Chemotype-I is characterized by α -kessyl acetate (**10**), valeracetate (**11**) and 8-epikessyl glycol diacetate (**12**) whereas the chemotype-II species contain maaliol (**13**) and kessanyl acetate (**14**). The *V. himalayana* GRUB. had maaliol, valeranone (**15**), kessane (**16**) and α -kessyl acetate as major compounds and *V. pyrolaefolia* DECNE. contained patchouli alcohol (**17**) and valeranone as markers. Epoxysesquithujene (**18**), a novel sesquiterpenoid has also been isolated in chemotype- I of *V. hardwickii* var. *hardwickii*¹⁶. Valeranone, maaliol, α -kessyl acetate, and

kessane are the major constituents of the essential oil from the roots of *V. himalayana*. Based on the morphological similarity¹⁷ between *V. wallichii* and *V. pyrolaefolia*, the latter is often collected together with the former for commercial purposes, nevertheless, there is no similarity with respect to the major constituents of their oils. Valeranone, the major constituent of *V. pyrolaefolia*, has not been noticed in *V. wallichii*^{18,19}.

Two valepotriates, 1-homoisovaltrate (**19**) and isovaleroxy hydroxydidrovaltrate were isolated from methylene chloride extract of the rhizomes of *V. pyrolaefolia* collected from alpine meadows of Kumaun Himalaya. The structures were elucidated by means of their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra. Isovaleroxy hydroxydidrovaltrate was isolated from methylene chloride extract of the rhizomes of *V. wallichii* DC. chemotype-I while the chemotype-II contains 11- α -acevaltrate (**20**). The structures were elucidated by means of their ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra²⁰.

C. Asteraceae

Tanacetum nubigenum Wall. :

The genus *Tanacetum* is commonly known as Tansy. *T. nubigenum* Wall. is a sub-alpine herb exists as 3 chemotypes. Chemotype-I contained (-)-*cis*-chrysanthenol and its esters (**21a-21f**), esters of exo-6-hydroxycamphor-3,6,6,9-bisepoxyfarnesa-1,7(14),10-trienes and 6,9-epoxyfarnesa-1,7(14),10-trien-3-ols (**22a-22e**)²¹ while second chemotype possessed (3*R*,6*R*)-tetrahydro-6-ethenyl-2,2,6-trimethyl-4*H*-pyran-3-acetate [(3*R*,6*R*)-linalool oxide acetate] (**23**) along with 2-hydroxy-4,6-dimethoxyacetophenone, (*E*)- (**24**) and (*Z*)-2-(2,4-hexadiynylidene)-1,6-dioxaspiro[4,4]non-3-ene²². Bornyl acetate was the major oil constituent in *T. nubigenum* third chemotype²³.

Erigeron species

Erigeron karwinskyanus, a small herb shows strong biological activity against *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium* and *Fusarium* species. It possessed acetylenic esters viz. *cis*- and *trans*-lachnophyllum and *cis-2-cis-8-*, *cis-2-trans-8-*, *trans-2-cis-8-* and *trans-2-trans-8-*matricaria esters²⁴. 3-Hydroxy-4-pyrone 3- α -D-glucopyranoside (**25**), a novel glucoside has been isolated from aerial parts of *E. karwinskyanus*²⁵. Three other *Erigeron* species viz. *Erigeron mucronatus*, *E. annuus* and *E. karwinskyanus* growing in sub-alpine region also revealed occurrence of isomeric polyacetylenic constituents viz. matricaria and

lachnophyllum esters which accounted for 83.3%, 69.3% and 30.1% of the essential oils from these species, respectively. In addition, the bioactivity results show the potential of *Erigeron* species for development of selective and natural fungicides against microbial phytopathogens which cause severe destruction to crop, vegetable and ornamental plants²⁶.

Senecio chrysanthemoides DC.

Two new eudesmanolides viz. 1 α -acetoxy-4 α -hydroxy-5 α ,6 β ,7 α ,11 β -*H*-eudesm-2-en-12,6-olide (**26**) and 1 α -acetoxy-3 α -hydroxy-5 α ,6 β ,7 α ,11 β -*H*-eudesm-4(15)-en-12,6-olide (**27**) have been isolated and characterized from the aerial parts of *Senecio chrysanthemoides* and characterized by X-ray crystallography²⁷.

D. Apiaceae

Pimpinella diversifolia DC.

It is widely distributed at 2,000 to 3,500 m altitude. The ethanolic extract of its seeds has been reported to be strongly fungitoxic and extract of the whole plant to possess spermicidal activity in rat semen. Six new compounds viz. (+)-4-methoxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)phenyl-*Z*-2-methyl-2-butenoate, 4-methoxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)phenyl isobutyrate (**28**), 1-angelyloxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)-4-isobutyryloxybenzene, 1-isobutyryloxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)-4-angelyloxybenzene, 1,4-diangelyloxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)benzene and 1,4-diisobutyryloxy-2-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)benzene (**29**) were isolated by extensive reverse phase chromatography (prep. HPLC) and characterized by taking high resolution EI-MS, ¹H- and ¹³C NMR data. The acetate derivatives such as 2-methoxy-4-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)benzene and 4-methoxy-4-(*E*-3-methyloxiranyl)benzene were synthesized and their ¹³C NMR data were recorded to confirm the substitution pattern in reported compounds^{28,29}.

Selinum tenuifolium Wall.

The aromatic herb gave 3,5-nonadiyne is the major constituents of the leaf oil which is almost single constituent of root oil. The report of occurrence and synthesis of 3,5-nonadiyne from any natural source was done for the first time³⁰.

E. Lamiaceae

Lamiaceae is a cosmopolitan family with natural occurrence of 421 species in 41 genera in Uttarakhand.

Mentha species

The genus *Mentha* has since long been of commercial interest because of its useful terpenoid constituents. *Mentha* species of different origins exist as large number of chemotypes and hybrids. The terpenoid composition of *Mentha longifolia* subsp. *Himalaiensis*, was determined. The spectral data confirm the presence of *cis*-piperitone oxide and piperitenone oxide as the major components³¹. The wild *Mentha longifolia* (Linn.) Huds. (syn. *M. sylvestris* Linn.), a common green spice, collected from different regions of Kumaon Himalaya has revealed carvone as major constituent which varied from 61.1–78.7% in the oil. These results are significant and have commercial potential because of very high content of carvone³².

Nepeta elliptica Royle.

A new naturally occurring crystalline diastereomer of nepetalactone viz. (7*R*)-*trans,trans*-nepetalactone (**30**) has been identified as the major component, of the essential oil of *Nepeta elliptica*³³. Coleon U (**31**), coleon U 12-methyl ether and dehydro coleon U 12-methyl ether (**32**) and its 7-(1-methylethenyl) homologue were identified in the chloroform extract of *Nepeta elliptica*³⁴.

Nepeta leucophylla Benth.

Three new iridodial derivatives iridodial- β -monoenoil acetate (**33**), dihyroiridodial diacetate (**34**) and iridodial dienol diacetate (**35**) have been isolated from the essential oil of *Nepeta leucophylla*^{35,36}. Iridodial- β -monoenoil acetate and actinidine (**36**) were screened for antifungal activities. Iridodial- β -monoenoil acetate was most effective against *Sclerotium rolfsii*, while actinidine isolated from *Nepeta clarkei* was highly active against *Macrophomina phaseolina*³⁷.

Nepeta govaniana Benth.

Nepeta govaniana Benth. collected in the flowering stage from the Garhwal region showed pregeijerene (38.4%), (+)-isoiridomyrmecin (16.5%) (**37**) and 4 α ,7 α ,7 α -nepetalactone (13.9%) were identified as flavour chemicals. The structure of (+)-isoiridomyrmecin was established by X-ray crystallography³⁸.

Ajuga parviflora

Ajuga leaves are generally not attacked by insects.

Fourteen strong antifeedants compounds from *Ajuga parviflora* including three new neo-clerodane diterpenoids viz. ajugarin-I chlorohydrin (**38**), deoxyajugarin-I (**39**) and 3 β -acetoxy clerodinin C (**40**) were characterized from whole plant extract³⁹.

Ajuga macrosperma Wall. var. brevifolia Hook. f.

Ajugacetalsterones C (**41**) and D (**42**) and reviflorasterone (**43**) were isolated from *A. macrosperma* var. *breviflora* along with five known compounds, namely, 20-hydroxyecdysone, cyasterone, makisterone A, 20-hydroxyecdysone-3-acetate and 20-hydroxyecdysone-2-acetate based on extensive NMR studies⁴⁰.

Species Elsholtzia

Elsholtzia species are associated with chemical variations in their flavour chemicals, consequently possess different chemotypes within some of the species. *E. polystachya*, *E. incisa*, *E. blanda* and *E. eriostachya* were found to have 1,8-cineole, acylfuran, phenols, citral and linalool rich chemotypes within them. The major terpenoid constituents of some *Elsholtzia* species are tabulated as under :

<i>Elsholtzia</i> species	Chemical constituents
<i>Elsholtzia strobilifera</i> Benth.	Sabinene (5.61%), β -pinene (9.66%), (<i>E</i>)-ocimene (1.80%), pinocarvone (51.88%) and humulene (3.81%) ⁴¹
<i>Elsholtzia cristata</i> Willd.	1-Octen-3-ols (0.66%), 3-methyl-2-(3-methylbut-3-enyl)furan (0.89%) and 3-methyl-2-(3-methylbut-2-enyl)furan (88.74%) ⁴²
<i>Elsholtzia polystachya</i>	β -Pinene (3.57%), 1,8-cineole (20.25%), γ -terpinene (4.93%), <i>trans</i> -ocimene (13.08%), perillene (1.34%), caryophyllene (15.03%), 2-hydroxy-1,8-cineole (1.72%), α -humulene (2.32%), β -curcumene (2.12%) and germacrene-D (3.11%) ⁴³
<i>Elsholtzia flava</i> Benth.	Piperitenone (21.81%), anethole (11.42%), carvacrol (9.84%), α -cubebene (1.35%), caryophyllene (3.45%), γ -elemene (8.75%) and δ -elemene (1.98%) ⁴⁴
<i>Elsholtzia pilosa</i> Benth.	1,8-Cineole (49.94%), γ -terpinene (5.20%), linalool (2.30%), <i>cis</i> -verbenol (0.50%), pinocarvone (2.10%), myrcenol (1.10%), thymol (4.30%), α -terpinyl acetate (2.20%), caryophyllene (0.60%) and γ -cadinene (0.90%) ⁴⁵

F. Zingiberaceae

Various *Hedychium* species are used in traditional medicines for treatment of asthma, bronchitis, blood purification, gastric diseases, and as antiemetics, especially among the hill tribes of Uttarakhand. A phytochemical study of the rhizome essential oils of *H. spicatum* var. *autiaticum* revealed the presence of 1,8-cineole, α -cadinol, 10-epi- γ -eudesmol (**44**), elemol (**45**) and β -eudesmol (**46**)⁴⁶. This is unique composition as compared to previous reports of monoterpene rich essential oil from this species. A separate chemo-profile study on four different *Hedychium* species showed dominant presence of 1,8-cineole, sabinene and terpin-4-ol, while *H. aurantiacum* possessed terpin-4-ol, *p*-cymene, and bornyl acetate as the major entities. Similarly, *trans-meta*-mentha-2,8-diene and linalool (**47**) were noticed in *H. coronarium*. Three different collections of *H. spicatum* showed amazing differences in the relative contents of their essential oils, 1,8-cineole and 10-epi- γ -eudesmol being identified as markers for samples I and II, terpinen-4-ol and sabinene being the major compounds in sample III. The rhizome essential oils of the above species exhibited moderate-to-good Fe²⁺ chelating activity⁴⁷.

Lauraceae species

The leaf terpenoid compositions of nine Lauraceae species, viz. *Neolitsea pallens*, *Lindera pulcherrima*, *Dodecadenia grandiflora*, *Persea duthiei*, *Persea odoratissima*, *Persea gamblei*, *Phoebe lanceolata*, *Cinnamomum tamala* and *Cinnamomum camphora*, collected from the Himalayan region were examined in order to determine the similarities and differences among their volatile constituents. Furanos-sesquiterpenoids were the principal constituents of *N. pallens*, *L. pulcherrima* and *D. grandiflora*^{48,49}. (*E*)-Nerolidol, limonene, β -pinene and α -pinene were the major constituents of *P. duthiei*; α -pinene, sabinene and β -caryophyllene were predominant in *P. odoratissima*, while the oils of *P. gamblei* and *P. lanceolata* possessed β -caryophyllene as common major constituent. *C. camphora* and *C. tamala* were marked by the presence of camphor and cinnamaldehyde, respectively⁴⁹. Furanos-sesquiterpenoids were the principal constituents of *Neolitsea pallens* (59.5%), *Lindera pulcherrima* (79.3%) and *Dodecadenia grandiflora* (36.9%). The leaf oil of *Lindera pulcherrima* was characterized by a high

content of sesquiterpenoids (96.8%), dominated mainly by furano-sesquiterpenoids (79.3%). *Dodecadenia grandiflora* oil showed similarity to that of *Neolitsea pallens* and *Lindera pulcherrima* in having furano-sesquiterpenoids (36.9%) as major constituents. Monoterpene hydrocarbons (36.4%) and oxygenated sesquiterpenoids (35.7%) were abundant in *Persea duthiei*. The leaf oil of *P. odoratissima* was marked by dominant presence of hydrocarbons (73.7%). The leaf oil of *P. gamblei* was also marked by hydrocarbons (73.9%). It can be noted that *Persea duthiei*, *P. odoratissima*, and *P. gamblei*, though having uniform qualitative essential oil compositions, differ greatly in quantitative content. *Persea duthiei* and *P. odoratissima* are morphologically very similar but significantly different in their oil compositions. The leaves of *Cinnamomum tamala* are known for eugenol-rich essential oil, but the material from this region contained (*E*)-cinnamaldehyde along with linalool and (*E*)-cinnamyl acetate. Eugenol was not detected in natural samples of *C. tamala*. Leaf oil of *C. camphora* (cultivated) contained camphor as the single major constituent. Himalayan Lauraceae species may thus be grouped as furan-containing genera (*Neolitsea*, *Lindera*, and *Dodecadenia*), mono- and sesquiterpenoid-rich genera (*Persea* and *Phoebe*), and oxygenated monoterpene dominating genus (*Cinnamomum*). Furanogermentone, a constituent of the essential oil of *Neolitsea pallens* is also a constituent of Chinese and Japanese traditional medicinal plants and has been established as an allergy inhibitor and antiulcer agent. Furanodienone (**48**) and curzerenone (**49**) possess insecticidal activity and have also been shown to exhibit significant anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and analgesic activities.

The occurrence of ecotypes, chemotypes and genotypes even within single plant species suggest the need of careful chemoprofiling and detailed investigations on chemical analysis for novel molecules and bioactivity variations for commercial/pharmaceutical applications of such plant materials.

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